

To Practice Volleyball, It is Necessary to Develop Physical Qualities

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Annotation: This article discusses the impact of exercise in the form of volleyball on the physical development of schoolchildren and University students. The purpose of the article is the consideration of the exercise, the implementation of which helps in preparing for the game of volleyball, thereby affecting the physical quality of students.

Keywords: volleyball, physical qualities.

The purpose of the article - consideration of exercises, the performance of which helps in preparing for the game of volleyball, thereby affects the physical qualities of students.

Nowadays, volleyball is one of the most popular types of sports games. Everyone plays volleyball, both children and adults, on sports grounds, in the yard, on vacation. Volleyball has a positive effect on the general condition of our body and is a good means of promoting health and physical development. Many experts note that active volleyball exercises strengthen the musculoskeletal system.

Good general physical fitness is the basis for success in practicing and playing volleyball, because the functional capabilities of the body are revealed. But with special training, there may be negative consequences, because there is a discrepancy in the pace of motor abilities. Since the motor apparatus is a complex biomechanical system, very little is known about the management and functioning of which. Strength, agility, speed and endurance are the main qualities acquired in volleyball classes. Many movements are based on running, jumping and throwing, used in volleyball, are natural in nature, so children learn them quite easily with proper training. As our experts Belyaev A.V. and Savina M.V. note: "The motor activity of volleyball players, although characterized by high intensity, almost completely excludes high-quality running loads. All movements of volleyball players are either shock or shock-absorbing and precision in nature." [1]

Volleyball players should be able to interact with a moving ball, where the visual analyzer plays an important role. Have good coordination, as he must make an assessment of the removal of the ball and the speed of its approach. These qualities are improved if you constantly practice in the volleyball section.

During the game of volleyball, game situations are constantly changing, and during the game we can observe a variable intensity, thereby the students master the game techniques.

Zheleznyak Yu. D., Kleshchev Yu. N., Chekhov O. S. note that the variety of movements when playing volleyball affects the physical development of students and helps to increase their motor activity throughout the entire period of study, both at school and in the volleyball sports section.

[5]

From the above, we can note that volleyball, which inseparably combines running, jumping and throwing, is a good means of physical fitness. Students who study in the volleyball section develop good coordination, the ability to act in accordance with situations that arise during the game of volleyball, and be dexterous.

It should be noted that the motor activity of volleyball players changes with the advent of new tasks that can be solved during the game, both consciously and automatically.

In volleyball, a good eye is developing, as students must calculate their movements with the flight of the ball. Volleyball players have a feature of peripheral vision, since students arbitrarily switch and

distribute attention from the situation on the field when switching from defense and attack, in this regard, the tactical skill of the players develops. Our researchers noted that the body of schoolchildren and students involved in volleyball is comprehensively affected by speed-strength exercises. Other strength and endurance exercises have a less widespread effect.

I would like to note that in one of the physical qualities, a high indicator may depend on other physical qualities. Therefore, we can conclude that in order to cultivate physical qualities, they must be proportionately developed in electoral activities. In order to cultivate the physical qualities that are necessary for volleyball players, acyclic exercises are used, carried out in a game technique with various techniques.

In volleyball classes, very diverse tasks are solved: physical qualities are developed, complex motor skills and playing techniques are improved. It should be noted that the main motor actions of volleyball players are fast movements, jumps, falls.[2]

All motor actions are performed at risk and the player needs self-control and courage.

During the game, we know that all actions change. Therefore, in the classroom, a volleyball player needs to master the system of motor skills, which are developed from a large number of techniques of defense and attack. In game situations, there is a certain difficulty in applying all the techniques where the player is required to move accurately, as well as switch from one movement to another, which may be different in speed, character and rhythm.

Zheleznyak Y. D. wrote in his research: "That almost all actions of volleyball players occur on the basis of visual perceptions. The ability to see the position and movement of players on the court, the continuous movement of the ball, as well as the ability to quickly navigate in the prevailing conditions are the most important qualities of volleyball players. This places very high demands on the volume of the players' field of vision and the accuracy of their eye." [4]

If we analyze all the actions of volleyball players, they are automated, so that those actions that would seem to be built according to the type of complex reaction are built according to the type of simple one. All actions, accuracy and suddenness develop quickness of reaction, as well as develop the speed of movements that are associated with the high speed of the ball. In volleyball players, under the influence of training, such components of the latent reaction period as the moment of difference, recognition, and especially the choice of actions are minimized by developing an appropriate dynamic stereotype.

Volleyball is a game with a quick reaction, but you can't just trust it, because volleyball players need to anticipate various game situations.

The game of volleyball requires maximum responsiveness from each student. Consequently, in conditions of acute time shortage, the activity of a volleyball player is interconnected with the willingness to perform certain actions.

In volleyball classes, a lot of speed and reaction exercises are performed, where players must move quickly, exercises in which it is necessary to shorten the distance, increase speed, and also respond well to unexpected continuations in the game.

Performing throws, rapid movements, jumps, unexpected changes in direction of movement, sudden jerks, falls, rapid turns of the head when orienting, all this affects the vestibular apparatus.

Belyaev A., Bulykina L. In their research, they argue that in volleyball, the speed of muscle contraction is of primary importance, on which the effectiveness of performing techniques depends, it is necessary to apply a wide range of exercises aimed at developing muscle strength and the speed of their contraction. [2]

It should be noted from all the above that during the game of volleyball, it is typical for those involved to perform a variety of alternating movements. The rules of the game of volleyball force the player to obey and act in the interests of the team in order to achieve a common goal. Each player must act on

the field with maximum strength and capabilities in order to overcome difficulties in the course of wrestling. Studying the literature on the game of volleyball, we agree with researchers that volleyball contributes to the education of a sense of teamwork; perseverance, determination, purposefulness; attention and quick thinking; the ability to manage one's emotions; improvement of basic physical skills

Thus, in order for volleyball players to have high physical performance, schoolchildren and students should be motivated to study. For this purpose, competitions in OFP, volleyball between students, as well as regional competitions and various tournaments are held. All this causes schoolchildren and students to be interested in classes where they want to be the best in general physical fitness and join the main team to participate in competitions of various ranks.

For the education of various physical qualities, we would like to offer special physical exercises for the development of speed.

1. Running from the start from various positions, including from a sitting position, lying face down or up, lying flat, lying with your head in the opposite direction (relative to the direction of movement). Dosage: [5-6 times of 10-15 meters with an interval of 1.0-1.5 minutes] x 3-4 series after 2-3 minutes of rest. It is recommended to perform these exercises on cue, in a group or independently, but preferably with time control.
2. Running at a maximum speed of 30-60 meters. Dosage: 3-5 times x 1-3 series. Rest until breathing is fully restored.
3. Running at top speed on the "go": 10-30 meters from a 30-meter run. Perform the same as the previous exercise.
4. Fast running downhill (up to 15 degrees) with the setting to achieve maximum speed and frequency of movements at a distance of 10-30 meters from a 30-meter run. Dosage: 3-5 times 1-2 series.
5. Fast running in the park or in the forest with slopes and escapes from oncoming branches of bushes and trees. Dosage: fast running up to 10 seconds after
6. Moving on all fours with the maximum possible speed. Try to perform in a competitive manner, in relay races.
7. Performing individual hand or foot strikes at maximum speed into the air or on projectiles. To test your speed, you can use the following technique: hang a newspaper sheet and strike it. If the speed in the final part of the blow is high enough, then the newspaper sheet is easily "pierced" by the impact part of the arm or leg. Dosage: 3-5 series of 5-10 single strokes. If the speed of strokes decreases, the exercise should be stopped.
8. Applying a series of punches or kicks with maximum frequency in the air or on projectiles. Dosage: 5-6 series of 2-5 strokes for 10 seconds. Such fragments are repeated 3-4 times after 1-2 minutes of rest, during which it is necessary to completely relax the muscles that perform the main load in the exercise.
9. Consecutive application of a series of 10 punches or kicks followed by 20 seconds
10. Performing the maximum number of punches in an upward jump on the spot.
11. Performing fixed series of punches in jumping up on the spot with the concentration of effort in one of them. It is necessary to start with two strokes in each series, then gradually increase their number.
12. Rhythmic jumps with a skipping rope, trying to periodically "scroll" it with your hands more than once in one jump, gradually increasing the speed of rotation of your hands.

13. Jumps through a rope rotated by two partners, with periodic acceleration of its rotation to increase the speed of repulsion in a row in 1-3 jumps: 3-4 jumps at a normal pace + 1-3 times in accelerated.
14. Deviations from the ball thrown by the partner, gradually reducing the distance or increasing the speed of throws. This exercise is the basis of a number of outdoor games.
15. Catching a ball thrown by a partner, protecting the "gate".
16. Running up the stairs with maximum frequency and speed. This exercise is usually performed on the steps of the forest
17. Multiple jumps (triple, fivefold, tenfold) with one or two legs. Dosage: [3-4 jumps] X - 3 series.
18. Jumping over evenly spaced athletics barriers: [5-6 barriers 76-100 cm high] x 5-10 times. Perform with the installation for "instantaneous" repulsion.
19. Jumping off a stand with a height of 30-60 cm followed by "instantaneous" repulsion in a jump up or forward. This exercise requires a fairly good speed and strength training. Therefore, it should be performed after preliminary training in jumping and sprinting exercises. Dosage: [5-8 jumps] x 1-3 approaches.

Sample exercises for the development of speed and strength qualities of volleyball players: - shuttle running with a hand touching the offensive line and the front line; the same as the first stop, but with a fall on the lines;

- imitation of blocking along the entire length of the grid (jumping on the block in zones 2, 3,4); imitation of an attacking blow with a fall after landing on the chest
- abdomen (hip – back); - defensive actions in pairs (only one athlete is protected); an attacking kick from a run-up from zone 4 (2, 3) with an intensity of 5 blows in 20 seconds;
- a series of falls, between falls – moving in two or three steps. - exercises for the education of high-speed endurance are used in the middle and at the end of the training session.
- an attacking run-up shot from zone 4 from the first pass of the ball (5-6 strikes) without pauses of rest between beats. After a series of strikes, the attacker "picks up" 3-4 balls in defense - performing the second transfer of the ball with a preliminary exit from zone 1(5) After completing the transfer, the passing player quickly returns to the starting position. The most acceptable means for strength training of volleyball players are:
 - ✓ exercises in overcoming their own weight (squats, pull-ups, jumping exercises, etc.);
 - ✓ exercises with a partner (squats, pulling, pushing, pulling, etc.);
 - ✓ exercises with weights (kettlebell, barbell, etc.);
 - ✓ exercises using elastic resistance objects (expanders, rubber harnesses, elastic balls, etc.);
 - ✓ exercises using training devices; basic and simulation exercises with small weights (in a training vest, with cuffs on the wrists, hips, etc.).
- shock exercises in which one's own weight increases due to the inertia of a freely falling body (jumping from a pedestal with instantaneous subsequent jumping up) Approximate exercises for developing strength muscles of the arms and shoulder girdle:
 - ✓ flexion and extension of the arms, lying down (options: one hand on the other; with alternate lifting of the legs; with a clap of the palms at the moment of repulsion; alternate repulsions with a turn around the feet; with support on the fingers, etc.).
 - ✓ movement on the hands, the legs are supported by a partner.
 - ✓ throws stuffed balls with one and two hands from a running start, from a place, sitting on the floor.

- ✓ standing on a rubber shock absorber, holding the ends of the shock absorber in your hands, bending your arms at the elbows to the chest (options: raising your arms forward-up, to the sides - up, circular rotations with your hands).
- ✓ striking movement of the arm when attacking
- ✓ circular rotation of the hands with weights. - movement, sitting in a stop, moving your arms and legs.
- ✓ movement on the hands in a lying position without the help of legs. Approximate exercises for developing the strength of the muscles of the trunk: - lying on your back with your hands behind your head – raise your torso with a forward tilt until your elbows touch the floor. - the same, but hands on the floor, palms down, legs together, lift straight legs up and lower them to the right, then to the left. - lying face down on the floor, alternately or simultaneously lifting and holding arms and legs, bending over. - bending back and forth, lying with your hips on the gym bench, your legs are held by your partner. - it's the same with weights.

Sample exercises for developing leg muscle strength.

- running up and down the stairs. - squats on two legs, on one leg.
- Pulling and pushing the partner away.
- "Cockfight" (both partners, jumping on one leg, jostle with their shoulders). - squats with weights (half-squat; slow squat).
- jumping out with weights on your shoulders. - in a sideways lunge, the transfer of body weight from one leg to the other. - carrying a partner on your shoulders (back).

Approximate exercises for the development of jumping ability:

- jumping from a place, from a running start, taking out a basketball shield, a ring.
- jumping from a deep squat. - jumping on one and two legs in place and moving face forward, sideways and backwards; the same with weights.
- multi-jumps at the shield with a touch at the maximum height for the student. - running jumps with getting the metric mark as high as possible.
- jumping over obstacles (rubber, twine, stuffed balls, etc. can be used as obstacles) - jumping and jumping on a pedestal (the height of the pedestal is 0.5 – 0.8 m). - jumping rope on two legs (options: from foot to foot, with forward movement, on one leg, in a squat, with double
- simulations of attacking blows in a jump from a place, from a running start. - simulation of blocking in place and after moving. - simulations of a block, an attacking blow, a block, an attacking blow, etc. - attacking blows through the net after a run-up from different gears along the trajectory.
- sample exercises for the development of jumping endurance of volleyball players:
- jumping with a barbell on the shoulders from a deep squat (barbell weight – 20 kg) – 1.5 min;
- jumping to a height of 80-100 cm (60-80' cm for women) – 1 min; simulated blocking – 1 min;
- the player consistently simulates an attacking strike and blocking (strike – two blocks), after which he quickly retreats to the line of attack to perform the exercise again – 1.5 – 2 minutes;
- blocking of in-line attacking strikes in zone 2, 3, 4 - 1.5 -2 min. blocking of alternate attacking strikes in zones 2,3,4,3,2,3,4,3,2.
- an attacking strike from the first gear in zone 4, here blocking - an attacking strike from the opposite side of the court. Perform the same actions in zones 3,2,3,4.

Approximate exercises for the development of volleyball players' playing endurance:

- jumping on one leg, pulling the hips up to the chest, – 15 jumps on each leg; - somersault forward, jerk 6 m, throw on the chest (roll onto the back), 10 jumps from a deep squat – 2-3 times;
- shuttle running from the front line to the line of attack and back with a throw with a throw (fall) on the chest (back) on the lines, without rest breaks – 5 falls; after 30 seconds. perform again; - imitation of an attacking kick with a run-up with a fall (throw) on the chest – back after landing - 10 jumps and falls;
- mobile game "Fight for the ball" (each team on its own court) – 3 min. The exercises are performed at the fastest possible pace. In each pause, exercises are used, different in their effects. This type of training work makes it possible to improve technical and tactical skills, contributes to the education of speed, strength and volitional qualities.

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